

A0303

Status of HEXIS' SOFC Module Development

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Abstract

HEXIS develops and manufactures SOFC-based micro-CHP units for houses and small companies. The current generation of the HEXIS SOFC unit "Leonardo", which has been developed in the past few years, is being tested both, in field and in the lab. Additionally, the development of the next generation system ("da Vinci") is also ongoing and the first 10 prototypes have been manufactured and are being tested.

Since the 1st of June 2020, Hexis has become part of mPower GmbH, based in Dresden, Germany, and whose parent company, h2e Power Systems Private Limited, is an Indian high-tech company based in Pune, India.

This paper will report the latest results of short-stack tests and of module and system tests based on the current system generations combined with historical data of the earlier Galileo systems. These include tests running for more than 52,000 h. Moreover, results of the "da Vinci" modules, reaching electrical efficiencies of 50 % AC, net and total efficiencies of 95 % (LHV) will be shown.

Long-term and cyclic testing of systems in lab tests as well as results on robustness and performance in the field will be discussed. Degradation rates as low as approx. 0.35 % / kh, i.e. 13 mΩ cm² / kh could be shown on the short-stack level for over 52,000 h. These stacks were analyzed with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at regular intervals, which could provide valuable insights in understanding fundamental degradation mechanisms for long term operation of SOFC stacks.

As of date, the field tests with the "Vitovalor SA-2" systems, which are based on the Leonardo SOFC unit have been running for approx. 10,000 h, with a lifetime prognosis of approx. 40,000 h.

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Introduction

HEXIS is developing and manufacturing SOFC-based micro-CHP units for houses and small companies. For the past few years, we have been developing the new generation (Leonardo) of the HEXIS SOFC units, which are now running in field and lab tests. Additionally, the development of the next system (da Vinci) generation was kicked off and first results on prototype level were achieved.

Since the 1st of June 2020, Hexis has become part of mPower GmbH, based in Dresden, Germany, whose parent company h2e Power Systems Private Limited, is an Indian high-tech company based in Pune, India. A corresponding purchase agreement was signed and consummated between mPower and Viessmann. The agreements also include the future cooperation of Hexis with the previous owner for the supply of SOFC fuel cell units. As Viessmann had announced, the family-owned company is focusing on the system integration of fuel cell modules into its own energy systems.

The Galileo 1000 N system was available on the market between 2013 & 2018. 105 Galileo systems are still in operation and provide important information on durability of components and SOFC stacks.

1. Approach: Concept of the HEXIS SOFC systems

While the technical market readiness could be demonstrated with the previous Galileo system back in 2013, it was clear that manufacturing costs must be significantly decreased, and that component availability will become an issue for some parts of the Galileo. Therefore, the development of a next-generation HEXIS- μ CHP-system (internal name Leonardo) was started a few years ago. The aim was to significantly cut down manufacturing and component costs. The SOFC stack itself remained largely unchanged, so that most of the experience gained in the last years with the Galileo systems could be transferred to the new system. Also, catalytic partial oxidation (CPOx) was retained to reform natural gas.

The Leonardo unit (see Figure 1), like the Galileo, is made to fit in single-family homes and small multi-family homes. It has an electrical power output of approx. 1.5 kW_{el}, an electrical efficiency of 40 % (AC, net, LHV) and a total efficiency of 95 % (LHV).

As one path to market, the units will be mainly sold to HVAC OEMs to integrate it in their heating system portfolio. One of the first OEM that will integrate the SOFC unit as part of its Fuel Cells System Vitovalor SA-2 is Viessmann, HEXIS's former parent company.

Figure 1: HEXIS' new generation SOFC-unit "Leonardo" integrated into a Viessmann Vitovalor SA-2.

2. Results

Short Stack long-term testing

In order to enable reliable prediction of long-term system performance, the generation of fuel cells employed in the Leonardo systems were tested extensively early-on in the development process. In 2014, two short stacks were started on steady-state conditions and under CPOx reformed natural gas. These tests have been monitored in regular intervals by I-V curves and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Long term data from these measurements is shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Long-term test data of a 5-cell short-stack operated with 4 g/h CPOx-reformed natural gas per cell (i.e. 51 W, LHV) for more than 52,000 h at 850°C. Combined Test: 50 Redox-cycles + 10 Thermo-Redox-cycles + steady-state operation. Average voltage degradation (2000 – 50,000 h): 2.9 mV/ kh, i.e. 0.35 % per 1,000 h. The test had to be stopped due to a failure of the test station.

Figure 3: Long-term test data of a second 5-cell short-stack operated with 4 g/h CPOx-reformed natural gas per cell (i.e. 51 W, LHV) for more than 49,000 h at 850°C. Combined Test: 50 Redox-cycles + 10 Thermo-Redox-cycles + steady-state operation. Average voltage degradation (2400 – 45,000 h): 2.5 mV/ kh, i.e. 0.3 % per 1,000 h. At approx. 49,000 hours, a test station failure occurred, the test stand could be repaired, and the test continued, although the voltages started decreasing earlier (i.e. @ 47,000 h), they were able to recover after repair (not shown).

Figure 2 shows results of a long-term test on short-stack level that has been shown (in its “younger” state) many times before [1, 2]. The test was a combined test including cycles and long-term operation: first 50 redox cycles, then 10 thermo-redox-cycles till < 300 °C followed by steady-state operation. Later, a few additional thermo-redox-cycles were conducted, part of them planned, to investigate the cycling-sensitivity of “aged” stacks, part of them occurred unintentionally because of lab and test-rig failures. The observed voltage degradation rate is 0.35 % per 1000 h (i.e. 2.6 mV per 1000 h) based on the steady-state operation. As shown earlier [2], this voltage degradation corresponds to an ASR-degradation of approx. 13 mΩ cm² / kh and approx. 75 % of that degradation is stems from ohmic resistances.

Until the beginning of 2020, the stack had survived all the intended and unintended test conditions. The stack performance then dramatically decreased (i.e. loss of voltage during loading), and during dismounting the stack it became clear, that the reformer module was significantly deformed resulting in a huge leakage in the gas path and as a result in the loss of stack performance.

Figure 3 displays similar data for the “younger” brother, which was started slightly later than the one mentioned above. The test conditions and behaviour are quite similar, voltage degradation was slightly lower (i.e. 2.5 mV per 1000 h). Also, this stack showed a decreasing voltage in the beginning of 2020, in this case due to a failure of the de-sulphuration unit caused by a local sulphur peak in the natural gas supply. Following the replacement of the de-sulphuration unit and a short operation at higher temperatures (900 °C), cell voltages stabilized and recovered to almost old values. After a “recover” period the test station is now operating at old conditions again (i.e. 850 °C) and results so far seem to be promising.

Due to the test station failure of the first short-stack, it was possible to investigate the oxide scale growth of the CFY interconnects. As reported earlier, oxide scale growth under the conditions present in the Hexis stack appeared to be more severe on the anode side of the interconnect, while the cathode side of the interconnect showed only thin oxide scales. This observation falls in line with past reports and is due to the imminent chromium evaporation process present at high oxygen partial pressures [3].

Figure 4: Cross-sections of an interconnect with anode side (left) and cathode side (right) contact ribs. The interconnect belonged to the short-stack discussed in Figure 2 and had been exposed to operating temperature of 850 °C for more than 52,000 h.

System Long-term Testing

The development of the new fuel cell unit *Leonardo* is in finalisation. Figure 5 shows results from field testing with 3 systems installed at end-customer-sites. All systems deliver around 1650 W_{el} DC, matching well to the targeted 1505 W_{el} (AC, net). To achieve this, gas inputs are set to 3800 - 3900 W depending on gas-quality, installation conditions and measurement accuracy, corresponding to 38 – 40 % electrical efficiency (LHV, AC, net).

Over 13,500 h, the gas input at maximum modulation point increases slightly to keep the electrical output constant despite the inherent stack degradation. The inherent degradation is in the same range as for the short-stacks and the former Galileo stacks, so that lifetimes of more than 40,000 h are also expected for the new units.

The larger variations in gas input and the corresponding electrical output modulations are due to heat demand variations at the installation sites, so that the heat-demand-driven system is modulating down when less heat is needed in the houses. At the minimum operating point, heat output is around 650 W_{thermal}, which fits well to the heat demand for warm water generation at the installation sites, displaying that an all-year-round operation is suitable, as long as a normal warm water demand is there. At the minimum operating point, electrical power output is still at approx. 400 W, fitting well to the baseload electrical consumption of the households.

Figure 5: Electrical power output and gas input vs. operation time of a field test system from the current generation. The variations in gas input are due to heat demand variations in the installation sites, while the gas input at maximum power output is slightly increased to keep the electrical power output constant. Operating temperature approx. 830°C.

Demonstrator System with Steam-reforming

For the future, it is planned to equip systems with an in-built steam reformer to achieve higher electrical efficiencies. A demonstrator has been setup based on the Leonardo fuel cell module and modified to a new reformer design. For this, the number of cells per stack were reduced from 60 to 50. The nominal fuel input was reduced to 2500 W (LHV, natural gas). Figure 6 shows the stack performance and the I-V curve. The demonstrator system reached a maximum DC-efficiency of 58.9% at 1470 W electrical power output (DC), corresponding to an AC, net efficiency above 50 %. It achieved similar total efficiencies of more than 94 %, like the CPOx systems (at 30°C circuit return temperature) and was operated in a self-sustaining mode regarding process-water (i.e. the water needed for steam-reforming was condensed from the exhaust gases) at circuit return temperatures up to 45°C. This demonstrator has now been operating for 10,000 hours.

Figure 6: Voltage, el. power output and electrical efficiency of the “da Vinci” demonstrator system operated on 2500 W Natural Gas. Peak electrical efficiency: 58.9 % DC. Operating Temperature 850°C.

Conclusions and Outlook

HEXIS has developed its next generation SOFC-based μ -CHP unit, with the final version now running in field-tests. A demonstrator system shows electrical efficiencies of more than 50 % AC net, which will form the basis for the next generation of systems.

With its new parent companies, mpower and h2e, HEXIS will not only become the supplier of SOFC units to its former parent company Viessmann, but will also be open to supply its fuel cell units to other OEMs. Moreover, together with h2e and mpower, it is intended to expand the Hexis product portfolio to other applications e.g. in agriculture and/or for power supply of distant rural areas. Additionally, the product portfolio of HEXIS, mPower and h2e will also include other SOC applications like electrolysis and P2X applications in the future.

Acknowledgements

HEXIS was supported for the work presented by the German Federal Ministry of Transport and digital Infrastructure within the “National Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology Innovation Programme” in the two projects Leonardo (project Nr. 03BH105) and Leonardo II (project Nr. 03BH214A). The work on the steam reforming concept is supported by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) within the project “da Vinci”.

References

- [1] Andreas Mai, Jan Gustav Grolig, Michael Dold, Felix Vandercruysse, Roland Denzler, Bernhard Schindler, Alexander Schuler, 13th European SOFC Forum, Lucerne, A0301, 2018
- [2] Andreas Mai, Jan Gustav Grolig, Michael Dold, Felix Vandercruysse, Roland Denzler, Bernhard Schindler, Alexander Schuler, ECS Transactions, 91(1), 63-70, 2019
- [3] Jan Gustav Grolig, Gino Longo, Andreas Mai, ECS Transactions, 91(1), 2181-2188, 2019

*Keywords: EFCF 2020, SOx
Session A03: Technology status at industry and major groups I*